

Formation Constants of the Chelates of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene- α -Naphthylamine with Some Bivalent Metal Ions

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Manuscript received 17 April 1978, revised 14 August 1978, accepted to October 1978

Potentiometric studies have been carried out on metal complexes of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene- α -naphthylamine. The dissociation constants ($\text{p}K_1$ and $\text{p}K_2$) of the reagent and the formation constants of its metal complexes have been determined by Bjerrum's method at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at ionic strength 0.1 M in 75 : 25 percent (v/v) dioxan-water medium. The order of stability of chelates is found to be $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{UO}_2^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Cd}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+}$.

LITERATURE survey indicates that no systematic study of the stabilities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene- α -naphthylamine with bivalent metal ions appears to have been carried out.

In the present communication, the successive stability constants of the complexes of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene- α -naphthylamine with some bivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The Corning model 12, a precision research pH meter with a wide range glass electrode and a calomel electrode system was used for pH measurements. With improvements in the performance of commercially available glass electrodes, glass electrode in conjunction with a reference calomel electrode is now incorporated in most of the modern meters similar to the one used in this study. Thus both electrodes dip into the titrating mixture without vitiating any of the results. The pH meter used in this study has an arrangement for normal and expanded scale. The smallest scale division on the expanded scale is 0.005 pH unit.

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene- α -naphthylamine was synthesised and repeatedly crystallised to get an analytically pure sample (m.p. 179°)².

All the chemicals used except the ligand and the perchloric acid were of B. D. H. analytical grade. The perchloric acid used was of E. Merck G. R. grade.

The medium of titration was dioxan-water mixture containing 75 per cent (v/v) of dioxan. The dioxan used for the experiments was purified by the

method described by Vogel³. Distilled water, redistilled over alkaline potassium permanganate and made free from carbon dioxide by boiling, was used throughout the investigation. Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain a constant ionic strength (0.1M). The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling nitrogen gas through solutions. All the metal perchlorate solutions were standardised complexometrically⁴ by E. D. T. A. titrations. All measurements were made at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (1.01 M) solution, keeping the total volume 40 ml.

(i) 5 ml of (0.16 M) HClO_4 + 5 ml of (0.64 M) NaClO_4 + 30 ml of dioxan.

(ii) 5 ml of (0.16 M) HClO_4 + 5 ml of (0.64 M) NaClO_4 + requisite amount of the reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml. of dioxan.

(iii) 5 ml of (0.64 M) NaClO_4 + 5 ml of (0.008 M) metal salt solution in (0.16 M) HClO_4 + requisite amount of the reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxan.

The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti¹ was applied to find out the value of \bar{n} and $\text{p}L$.

Results and Discussion

In the ligand it is the chelated phenolic "OH" group which takes part in the complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions

during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y' the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

From the titration curves using the solution (I) and (II), \bar{n}_A values at various 'B' values (pH meter readings) were calculated, and the curve between 'B' and the corresponding \bar{n}_A values was plotted. The formation curve extends over a range $0.4 < \bar{n}_A < 1.6$ and is wavelike. This indicates the formation of the species HL and H_2^+L , i.e. the protonated nitrogen and the phenolic hydrogen are completely dissociable in steps, separable. The value of pK_2^H could be evaluated from half integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 1.5$ and pK_1^H could be evaluated from half integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$

A plot of $\log (\bar{n}_A / 1 - \bar{n}_A)$ against 'B' was drawn and a plot of $\log (2 - \bar{n}_A) / (\bar{n}_A - 1)$ against 'B' was also drawn, (but they have not been included for economy of space) and from these curves the values of practical pK_1^H and pK_2^H were evaluated. The two values of pK_1^H and pK_2^H each, agree quite well, with those obtained by half integral method.

From the titration curves of solutions (II) and (III) \bar{n} and pL values were evaluated. The \bar{n} values obtained are upto 1.0 and hence $\log K_1$ values only could be determined by half intergral and graphical methods except in the case of Cu^{2+} where $\log K_2$ value has also been determined.

The \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal-complexion equilibria. From these formation curves the values of stability constants, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were computed which correspond to pL values at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and $\bar{n} = 1.5$, respectively.

A plot of $\log (\bar{n}' / 1 - \bar{n})$ against pL for different metal systems was also drawn. From these curves the values of $\log K_1$ were evaluated. The plot of $\log (2 - \bar{n} / \bar{n} - 1)$ against pL for Cu^{2+} metal system was also drawn and from the plot, value of $\log K_2$ was evaluated but the plot has not been included for economy of space. The values obtained by both the methods agree quite well.

The most representative values are recorded in the Table 1.

TABLE-1. STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES (a)

	t = 25°			μ = 0.1				
Cations	H ⁺	Cu ²⁺	UO ₂ ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Cd ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Mg ²⁺
log K ₁	10.15	10.00	9.27	6.17	6.15	5.60	5.55	4.20
log K ₂	2.40	8.70	-	-	-	-	-	-

(a) H⁺, K₁ & K₂ correspond to the species LH and LH₂⁺ respectively while for metal ions K₁ and K₂ correspond the species ML₂ respectively.

The order of stability of bivalent metal chelates was $Cu^{2+} > UO_2^{2+} > Zn^{2+} > Cd^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > Co^{2+} > Mg^{2+}$.

The order is in accordance with that observed by Murakami *et al*, in their study with metal complexes of catechol derivatives for bivalent transition metal series⁵, except the Cd complexes not incorporated by them.

With regard to the metal ions UO₂²⁺ and Cu²⁺ the order of the log K reported in the literature vary for N-O and O-O and other combinations of N and O as donor atom sets. The general trend is UO₂²⁺ < Cu²⁺ for O-O donors⁶. In the case of N-O donors however, a survey of the literature⁷⁻¹¹ reveals no definite trend even for the same series of ligands.

In the present case the order, Cu²⁺ > UO₂²⁺ is exhibited with the ligand under study.

To check the validity of log K₁ and log K₂ the standard deviation^{12,13} and limits of error were calculated for a few systems involving Cu(II), Zn(II), Mg(II), UO₂(II) and the results have been recorded in the Table-2.

Metal	log K ₁	Standard deviation	Limits of Error
Cu ²⁺	10.00	±0.065	±0.049
Zn ²⁺	6.17	±0.041	±0.032
Mg ²⁺	4.20	±0.067	±0.057
UO ₂ ²⁺	9.27	±0.020	±0.016

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to record their sincere thanks to Dr. D. G. Vartak, B. A. R. C., Bombay, and Dr. R. A. Kulkarni, Principal, Ramnarain Ruia College, Bombay-19, for their valuable suggestions and continuous encouragement.

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